

DYNAMIC AND VISUAL SIMULATION OF BIFACIAL ENERGY GAIN FOR PHOTOVOLTAIC PLANTS

Jesús Robledo^{1,*}, Jonathan Leloux¹, Babacar Sarr¹, Christian A. Gueymard^{1,2}, Anton Driesse³

¹ LuciSun, Rue Saint-Jean, 29, 1495 Sart-Dames-Avelines, Belgium

² Solar Consulting Services, P.O. Box 392, Colebrook, NH 03576, USA

³ PV Performance Labs, Emmy-Noether-Str. 2, 79110 Freiburg, Germany

*Phone: +34 656 37 59 74; E-mail: jesus.robledo@lucisun.com

ABSTRACT: Several simulation tools have appeared on the market to estimate the bifacial energy gain (BEG) of bifacial photovoltaic (PV) systems. These tools use two main families of methods that provide a quick estimation of the BEG or a detailed analysis of it, but not both. The current study presents an alternative methodology that provides both benefits using image generation techniques used in the video games and performing the computations in the GPU (Graphic Processor Unit) of the computer. The methodology used, as well as some examples of elaborate applications are presented, including interference with complex objects, movable elements (trackers), and intricate reflectance patterns for various reflecting materials characterized by their BRDF (Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function).

Keywords: Bifacial, PV, simulation, BEG, GPU, photovoltaic plants

1 INTRODUCTION

The simulation of the energy generated by bifacial photovoltaic (PV) modules is challenging because the irradiance received on their backside comes from different directions and sources. Bifacial PV has been experiencing a rapid growth in recent years. This translates into an increasing number and diversity of PV installations in the world with bifacial PV modules, and represents a large variety of scenarios, several of them with irradiance contributions involving peculiar reflectance patterns (irregular terrains, multiple reflective objects, tracking-induced dynamic movements...).

Several simulation tools have appeared on the market to estimate the bifacial energy gain (BEG) of bifacial PV systems. These tools use two main families of methods. The first family is composed of those methods that estimate the view factors at the back side of the PV modules using an analytical approach [1],[2]. This approach is relatively simple, but it can only produce a rough estimate of BEG. Another approach is to use raytracing, which makes it possible to obtain accurate simulations, but at the cost of extremely increased demands in computation time and resources [3].

This work presents a third and alternative method utilizing the processing power of the Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) of all modern computers. This avenue offers critical advantages compared to the existing approaches just mentioned. First, it is capable of reaching accuracy levels similar to raytracing. Second, it provides a dynamic and visual simulation that can be easily interpreted by non-experts. Third, it keeps the resource requirements relatively low. All this opens the door to a depth of analysis that was not achievable in practice before. The use of this method for the estimation of the bifacial energy gain is illustrated here for three typical kinds of application that are frequently encountered in the practice of solar engineering. The installation of bifacial PV modules on carports is used first to exemplify the method, because it presents several complex elements whose simulation require various steps. Two additional application cases are then presented: vertical bifacial PV

structures used in agrivoltaics, and PV modules in large-scale PV plants with or without tracking systems.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Method overview

The current method for the evaluation of the reflected irradiance on the backside of PV modules consists of breaking down the irradiance contribution (for the front side as well as for the rear side) incident on a single cell of each module into its diffuse and direct components. All the possible sources are grouped in a way that the overall irradiance incident on the plane of array can be obtained by transposing the direct and diffuse irradiance components that are either measured by radiometers or evaluated from spaceborne observations with appropriate radiative models. To obtain the total irradiance, I , incident on a tilted surface of any geometry, the general formulation proposed in [4] is such as:

$$I = f_b \text{DNI} \cos\theta + f_d R_d \text{DIF} + \text{REF} \quad (1)$$

where DNI is the direct normal irradiance, f_b is a sun shading factor, DIF is the sky diffuse horizontal irradiance, R_d is the diffuse transposition factor from horizontal to tilt (i.e., plane of array), f_d is a sky shading factor, and REF is the irradiance reflected by the surrounding ground. For monofacial PV applications, REF is typically calculated as a simple function of the global horizontal irradiance, GHI, using various simplifying assumptions that strongly impact the accuracy of this approach, as discussed in [5]. The diffuse transposition factor is usually calculated with one of a few transposition models that include anisotropic effects. One such model is that of Hay, whose accuracy has been amply validated [6],[7]. In the present context, one important advantage of this model is that it simply decomposes DIF into two components: an isotropic component, DIF_{iso} , and a circumsolar component, DIF_{circ} .

Rearranging Eq. (1), to split REF into a beam component and a diffuse component, the following expression is obtained:

$$I = (F_1 + F_2) \cdot (DNI + DIF_{\text{circ}}) \cos\theta + (F_3 + F_4) \cdot DIF_{\text{iso}} \quad (2)$$

where the F_i factors are functions that only depend on geometric, environmental, and material variables. They are time dependent but irradiance independent. The definition of those factors is as follows:

- F_1 is the fraction of direct incident sunlight incident on a cell. Consequently, F_1 is 1 if a cell is totally exposed to the sun, 0 if completely shaded, and intermediate in case the sun's disc is only partially shaded. The way to evaluate this factor is described in [8], and implies a shading computation that is based on shadow mapping techniques performed in the GPU.

- F_2 is a reflectivity factor that quantifies how the direct sunbeam are reflected over different ground elements and ultimately reach a specific solar cell, including the sun incidence angle influence. Consequently, the light source here is not constituted of parallel rays but of rays having any possible direction inside a 180° hemisphere, as seen from each cell in its specific orientation. The procedure for this computation is described in Sections 2.3 & 2.4.

- F_3 represents the ensemble of sky elements directly seen from the cell. As before, this requires a spherical view analysis, which is explained in Sections 2.3 & 2.4

- F_4 describes the reflection process over different objects that are seen from the unobscured sky. Again, this factor requires a spherical view analysis, which is explained in Sections 2.3 & 2.4.

2.2 Spherical view concept

In order to evaluate factors F_2 , F_3 and F_4 , the approach used here benefits from the power of GPUs in modern computers, as done in video games for fast picture generation. This provides a similar resolution as raytracing techniques, while requiring much less computing time. Essentially all objects that typically exist all around the installation's scene have simulated renderings that are included in accessible computer libraries. Hence, it is relatively easy to generate a realistic representation of any solar system and its environment.

From each side of each PV panel, a 180° spherical view over different points of the module is created, as shown in Figure 1. It is obvious that a tradeoff has to be considered between computation time and accuracy. An optimum can be found, depending on the number of viewpoints and their location over the PV plant.

Figure 1: Point of view selected on a module (left) and spherical views generated: Front side (top right) and rear side (bottom right).

The generation of pictures is done in a way that it is possible to identify each component of the scene and assign it a specific value at pixel level, which will be eventually integrated with the rendered picture to finally obtain the desired factor F_i . As a reference, the pictures shown in Figure 1 are generated at a resolution of 512×512 pixels—equivalent to more than 250,000 rays with the raytracing technique—and are obtained fast (≈ 10 – 20 ms per picture).

There are three possible contributors to the source of incident radiation:

1. Objects under shade (but able to reflect irradiance from the sky);
2. Objects under direct sunlight;
3. No objects: Sky directly visible.

The procedure followed to evaluate their respective impact is detailed in the following sections.

2.3 Selection of elements for the spherical view

In order to provide a proper value for each of the sky and surface elements, three main steps are followed.

The first step is to evaluate the potential for sun visibility from a particular object. This is a pure geometric parameter, which takes any value between 0 (sky fully blocked) and 1 (sky fully visible). Figure 2 shows an example of a carport with vehicles underneath.

Figure 2: Color-coded sky visibility potential for the carport scenario, and example of upward view from two points at ground level.

The second step is to apply reflectance properties to each element of the scene. A three-parameter Bidirectional Reflectance Function (BRDF) is considered as a function of sun incidence angle and spherical coordinates of the reflected direction, as shown in Figure 3. For each reflecting element irradiated by direct sunlight, this BRDF is directly used, whereas only its average is sufficient to quantify the diffuse reflected irradiance contribution from the sky over the element.

Figure 3: (Top) BRDF and angles definition; (bottom) example of different reflectance patterns in practice (Lambertian, semi-glossy, and specularly reflective).

The third step is to create a depth map reference from the sun's point of view with a parallel perspective. The goal here is to identify which elements are under shading when evaluating the irradiance coming from the sun and reflected on the surfaces. This is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Parallel projection from the sun's point of view to identify pixels under shading. Lighter colors indicate a higher depth in the view.

2.4 Combination of elements and spherical view generation

Based on the information obtained previously, it is possible to assign a color-code value to each element in the scenario and render it from the different points of view over each PV module, and ultimately obtain pictures such as the ones shown in Figure 5.

Each of the pictures are generated using a combination of the previous elements. For the objects under direct sunlight, an evaluation of each pixel in the spheric view is done for the following elements: the reflection value based on the BRDF at that point, defined with three angles as described in Figure 3 (θ_i : sun vector with surface normal where pixel is located, θ_r : reflected vector with surface normal, ψ_r : angle between the planes defined by sun vector and normal and the one defined by reflected vector and normal). Then, a check is done to verify if that pixel is shaded using the depth map obtained in the previous step. The integration of all the pixels of the spheric view provides the factor F_2 in Eq. (2), as shown in Figure 5a. For all the reflective objects or elements, the sky view potential is corrected by the corresponding diffuse albedo to generate the spherical view that provides the view factor F_4 in Eq. (2), shown in Figure 5b. For a direct view of the sky, which is needed to derive F_3 , a detailed anisotropic sky radiance model that depends on sun position, azimuth and elevation of the pixel, such as the one described in [9], is preferable to the simplistic isotropic sky radiance model [10], although this is more involved. The resulting F_3 estimate is shown in Figure 5d. For simplicity in this example, a homogenous (isotropic) radiance distribution is used, although the effect of the varying $\cos\theta_i$ (angle between the direction of the reflected ray and the normal to the observation point, as shown in Figure 3) is shown in Figure 5d. The spherical integration of each pixel's radiance value is shown in Fig. 5 for each view. The whole process is performed in the GPU.

Figure 5: Views from a specific solar cell of the carport canopy: a) elements under direct sunlight; b) diffuse irradiance view-factor reflection from the sky; c) shading factor for parallel rays on the front side of the same cell; and d) sky elements direct view from the front side.

2.5 View factors implementation at cell level

From the decomposition of the incident irradiance on each panel side, as described in Eq. (2), the following factors can be identified from the values indicated in Figure 5. For the front side: $F_1 = 0.56$ (Figure 5c), F_2 is considered negligible because of the low tilt angle of the installation (it could be computed as done in Figure 5a, but it is not shown here because it would be too low to be visible), $F_3 = 0.833$ (Figure 5d), whereas F_4 , just like F_2 , is considered negligible because of the low tilt angle of the installation (it could be computed as done for Figure 5b but again not shown here for clarity). Similarly, for the rear side: $F_1 = 0$ because the sun is on the front side, $F_2 = 0.062$ (Figure 5a), F_3 is considered negligible here because of the low tilt angle of the installation (although it could be computed as done in Figure 5d), and $F_4 = 0.047$ (Figure 5b).

The combination of those four factors with the irradiance values of that particular moment constitute the necessary inputs to compute the irradiance incident on each specific point along each panel side. Repeating the process for all elements into which the complete PV plant can be divided makes it possible to generate a heatmap of the irradiance's spatial distribution over both surfaces, as shown in Figure 6. That heatmap is a critical step toward analyzing possible inhomogeneities in the irradiance field and evaluating their electrical impact through a known mismatch methodology. This latter step is not part of the present contribution, which rather focuses on the irradiance distribution evaluation.

Figure 6: Spatial irradiance distribution over the complete PV generator.

The total computation time is obviously dependent on the number of viewpoints where the analysis is done. Hence, different optimal solutions can be found in the trade-off between computation time and local effects identification. The latter clearly conditions the level of accuracy in the end results. As a reference, and for the present example, the computational time needed for the complete irradiance evaluation over a point at a specific time moment is ≈ 50 ms (depending on hardware, but with a reference GPU: NVIDIA Quadro K620 with 384 cores).

3 APPLICATIONS

As an example of the possibilities offered by this powerful technique, two additional case studies that involve complex simulation scenarios are presented here. Their results are shown and only briefly discussed, highlighting some of the particularities of the evaluation in each case. These case studies are: a large PV plant with trackers, and a system made of vertical bifacial PV modules for agrivoltaics.

3.1 Ground-mounted PV plants with 1-axis tracking

This illustrative example is based on a 1-axis tracking system, as depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7: PV plant layout with 1-axis tracking system.

Here, the main influential characteristics are as follows:

- The module orientation is continuously variable during the day, and thus the sky-view potential is also variable.
- The rear structure creates shading and thus irradiance losses.
- The ground reflectance has specific directional properties.
- No defined “front” and “rear” side is considered with this configuration.
- The module’s orientation is variable and consequently the sky view potential is variable too.

As done in the other examples above, the first step consists in evaluating the sky visibility potential—in this case that of the ground. Here, however, this potential is dependent on the tracker rotation angle, hence this variable is now time dependent. An example of this potential at a particular time step can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Sky view potential close to mid-day.

The type of ground considered here is a plowed field. Its reflectance is determined using the Roujean model from the Sasktran Python library [11]. A depth map of the installation can be seen in Figure 9 for a particular moment in the morning. In this specific case, the depth map is mainly used to evaluate the shading pattern and intensity over the ground. It also supports the evaluation of those ground elements that can be in the shade for direct sunlight reflections. For a tracking installation with backtracking implemented, it is not expected that mutual shading exists between the modules. However, when the terrain is irregular and all the trackers have the same tracking algorithm, this depth map is helpful to identify possible mutual shadows and customize the backtracking algorithm.

Figure 9: Depth map from the sun’s point of view.

The spherical views for a particular instant are shown in Figure 10 for the front side and Figure 11 for the rear side. For this particular application, and by selecting a higher tilt angle than in the carport application, some of the contributions that were considered negligible in that

case are now significant, hence the results are split between the front side and rear side. To better distinguish the sides, a different texture is applied to each of them (bluish for the front one and black for the rear one). No information regarding mutual shading is included because a backtracking rotation algorithm is assumed.

Figure 10: (a)- Realistic simulated view from the front side, for reference; (b) - sky's direct view from the front side; (c) – view factor for diffuse reflection from the sky; (d) – elements under direct sunlight.

Figure 11: (a) – Realistic simulated view from the rear side, for reference; (b) - sky direct view from the rear side; (c) – view factor for diffuse reflection from the sky; (d) – elements under direct sunlight.

For the particular analysis of the irradiance incident on the rear side, two cases exemplify different module layouts: one with PV arrays formed by the installation of one row of PV modules mounted in portrait, or vertical mode (referred to as 1V), and another one with two rows

of PV modules mounted one on top of the other in vertical mode (2V). As can be seen in Figure 12, the 1V configuration (left side) has the tracker bar interfering with the rear side of the modules, creating a low irradiance area. This effect is not observed in the 2V configuration. However, to properly estimate the energy losses due to this effect, a detailed mismatch analysis of the non-homogenous irradiance distribution should be done and will be the objective of future studies.

Figure 12: Irradiance distribution heat map for 1V (top) and 2V (bottom) configuration.

3.2 Vertical bifacial PV for agrivoltaics

A general overview of a typical vertically mounted installation using bifacial PV modules for agrivoltaics can be seen in Figure 13. It consists of several rows of bifacial modules installed vertically, with a significant inter-row distance.

Figure 13: Vertical modules for agrivoltaics on an uneven terrain.

In this case, the main challenges are:

- Orientation of the modules – No pre-defined “front” and “rear” side is considered with this configuration.
- The irregular terrain induces complex shading and reflection characteristics.
- Grass is known to have intricate directional reflectance properties.

As explained in Sections 2.1 to 2.5, several sequential steps must be performed to obtain the incident irradiance distribution over each side separately. The initial step consists of obtaining the sky visibility potential for the reflective elements (i.e., only the ground in this case). The result of this calculation can be seen in Figure 14. The spatial distribution shows the loss of sky visibility from the ground close to the modules, as could be expected, but increasing quickly with distance from the structures. Moreover, some differences in the visibility

potential are found along the terrain due to the different tilt angles of the irregular surface, but these differences are small and cannot be detected with the contrast shown in the image.

Figure 14: Sky visibility potential from the ground.

The BRDF reflectance model implemented here is based on the Roujean model that is included in the Sasktran Python library [11]. The shape of its BRDF for a low sun angle can be seen in Figure 15. It predicts a higher reflectance for high incidence or reflected angles.

Figure 15: Directional BRDF implementation based on the Roujean model for green grass.

The depth map reference for shading analysis can be seen in Figure 16, where a low sun elevation angle is chosen to emphasize the contrast between the different elements.

Figure 16: Depth map from the sun's point of view.

An example of the different spherical views computed for a particular instant is shown in Figure 17. For this case, all the factors can be computed for both panel sides, but only some of them are presented for conciseness. Because no “front” or “rear” side can be defined in this case, the front side is supposed to be facing the sun for the sake of this picture. As done in the other examples above, a heatmap is generated based on the view factors obtained for different points along each panel side, also considering calculated values of diffuse

and direct irradiance.

Figure 17: (a) - elements under direct sunlight for the rear side; (b) - diffuse irradiance view factor reflection from the sky; (c) – realistic simulation view from the front side, for reference; (d) – direct view of sky elements from the front side.

A result from that analysis is shown in Figure 18, showing the situation at 8:30 AM (local time) at a site located at a latitude of 45°. The effect of ground shading on the rear side can be observed by a lower irradiance incident on the bottom part of the modules, whereas the distribution is reversed for the front side (because higher irradiance is received when closer to the ground). Additionally, some effects of the terrain’s slope can be observed in the top right corner of Figure 12, where the terrain is higher and freer of obstacles, thus inducing higher incident irradiance.

Figure 18: Irradiance heatmap analysis of the “front” side (top) and “rear” side (bottom).

4. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The GPU-based method presented here has already been used to assess the bifacial energy gain of many large bifacial PV plants totaling more than 1 GW since 2017, with a large diversity of applications. These include large PV plants with fixed structures or trackers, carports, canopies in rural areas, greenhouses, and vertical agrivoltaic structures. Several application cases have been illustrated in this article. The further development and scientific validation of this method is currently ongoing in the context of two European R&D projects: the H2020 project SERENDI-PV, and the COST project Pearl-PV. The method is still being improved to take

more difficult situations in consideration., given the increasing diversity of bifacial PV installations, and the scarcity of reliable monitored operational data that are currently available, more effort and more collaboration will be needed in the future in order to incorporate and validate new functionalities in the tool. In this context, collaboration proposals are welcome, on the research effort as well as on the analysis of the operation data of bifacial PV installations.

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